

HUMANITY LIVES IN A DIRECT CONNECTION WITH FINE ARTS

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Abstract. This scientific article discusses the high level of development of fine arts in our country and their unique role in human life. It also covers the fundamentals of teaching painting techniques, familiarising oneself with works of art, and overcoming some of the issues that arise in artistic analysis.

Keywords: Fine arts, Afrosiyob, Bolaliktepa, Varakhsha, painting, murals, miniatures, still lifes, simple pens, aesthetics, education, upbringing, beauty.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu ilmiy maqolada tasviriy san'atni vatanimiz hududida yuksak darajada rivojlanganligi hamda tasviriy san'atning inson hayotida beqiyos tutgan o'rni o'rganilgan. Shuningdek tasvirlash sirlarini o'rgatish, tasviriy san'at asarlari bilan tanishish va badiiy tahlil qilishda yuzaga kelayotgan ba'zi muammolarni bartaraf etishning dastlabki bosqichlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tasviriy san'at, Afrosiyob, Bolaliktepa, Varaxsha, rangtasvir san'ati, devoriy suratlar, miniatyura, natyurmort, oddiy qalam, metodika, estetik, ta'lim, tarbiya, go'zallik.

Аннотация. В данной научной статье рассматривается высокий уровень развития изобразительного искусства и уникальная роль изобразительного искусства в жизни человека нашей страны. Также освещаются начальные этапы обучения секретам живописи, знакомство с произведениями изобразительного искусства, преодоление некоторых проблем, возникающих при художественном анализе.

Ключевые слова: Изобразительное искусство, Афросиаб, Болаликтепа, Варахша, живопись, росписи, миниатюры, натюрморты, простой карандаш, эстетика, образование, воспитание, красота.

From time immemorial, our great ancestors have studied the secrets of the fine arts. At the same time, they strove to create invaluable examples of fine art for future generations. Talented painters and sculptors from different cultures created works that expressed positive concepts, reflecting feelings such as humanity and patriotism.

As human thinking matured from the most ancient times, so did the sense of beauty. Later, writing began to emerge in various forms and images. The need to create and later decorate everyday objects gradually developed fine arts from ancient times. Mental labour began to separate from physical labour. This was of great importance in the development of science and art. Examples of fine art allow us to study the history, beliefs, aesthetic worldview and lifestyle of our people. This forms the basis for the development of modern art.

Written sources, as well as various archaeological finds and cave paintings, show that fine art has existed since the time of primitive communities. Even in primitive communities, images were initially necessary for people to communicate with each other. During this era, primitive people depicted their imagination on rocks and stones. They used these images to express their thoughts.

Many of the primitive images found in Uzbekistan, such as those in Zaravutsay in the Surkhandarya region and in the Tagotash region of Jizzakh, are considered to be among the earliest examples of fine art. Uzbekistan has many examples of fine art. Notable examples include the colourful murals in Afrosiyob in the ancient city of Samarkand, Bolaliktepa in Surkhandarya, Varakhsha in Bukhara and Panjikent. During the Zoroastrian era, architecture, sculpture, painting, pottery and decorative arts developed uniquely. Following the introduction of Islamic culture, certain obstacles arose in the depiction of living beings and their forms. During this period, applied decorative arts, especially in connection with architecture, developed extremely well.

When we view fine artworks created by artists, we are impressed by the masterpieces that they have created with their skill, passion, and love. We are interested in how they mastered the secrets of depiction. If possible, we also desire to acquire priceless works of art created with such skill. Those who have not been trained as artists may think, "If only I could draw such wonderful, beautiful pictures!"

As can be seen from the above, all types and genres of fine art are of particular interest in our country, from young children to the elderly. However, to understand and think about works of fine art, one must have at least basic knowledge.

When a viewer approaches a work of art, they usually try to find out what is depicted and what the artist wants to convey. However, some people do not go beyond saying that the picture 'looks like' or 'does not look like', 'is good' or 'is bad'. Such evaluations are often made by people who are indifferent to fine art. In this regard, it should not be forgotten that the

ideological meaning of works of art is of primary importance. The viewer should know the name of the work, who created it, and the era or time it depicts.

Each artist creates works of fine art in their own unique way. They try to express their inner feelings and their perception of beauty through colours, lines and shapes. When works of fine art are created to their full potential, their unique and beautiful images attract people involuntarily. Looking at such unique works, each person forms their own thoughts about them.

Before we examine, understand and analyse works of fine art, let's consider the world around us. What is the place of fine art in our lives today? Some people ignore fine art, viewing it superficially and asking, 'Is painting even work?' If we look around us, we see that the decoration of squares, streets, circuses and luxurious buildings was all made possible thanks to the hard work of artists and sculptors. The inner beauty of our homes and the content of our schools, books, newspapers, and magazines are further enhanced by images. Even the colourful decorations on purchased items in markets and shops, from containers to labels, attract our attention. The shape, style and colour of textiles and everyday clothes are enriched thanks to the work of artists. These thoughts confirm that we cannot imagine clothing or home furnishings without images and colours. Each piece of furniture, with its various patterns, practical decorations, colours, and shades, has a special positive effect on a person. The carpets, rugs and colourful curtains that fill our homes each contribute to our well-being. The artistic decorations and overall appearance of holidays and events such as weddings, which take place in every Uzbek home, also have a positive aesthetic effect on people. Sometimes, when we look at the interior and exterior of our homes or the artistic decorations of wedding halls, we do not even notice that this process is related to fine arts. The tasteful placement and installation of new furniture and decorations in our homes also requires artistry. The colour and appearance of each selected item enhances the aesthetic appeal. In artistic apartment decoration, the harmony between each piece of furniture and its placement shows the homeowner's refined taste. This demonstrates that, even if not everyone holds a brush in their hands, they still live in a way that is closely connected to the fine arts.

Above, we considered how important fine arts are in human life. Of course, to make our lives more beautiful and meaningful, we must master the secrets of fine art. With this in mind, we will now offer some recommendations for learning to paint. Firstly, it is better to start mastering the secrets of fine arts in childhood and youth. Many young people in different regions of our country are highly interested in fine arts, love them with all their hearts, and have

great aspirations. Similarly, it is important to recognise the interests and aspirations of young people eager to learn the secrets of painting and guide them in the right direction.

To learn the secrets of drawing, it is first necessary to master pencil drawing techniques. This is because all artists, no matter what type or genre of fine art they create, start by drawing with a simple pencil. When starting to learn to draw, it is recommended that you draw simple subjects from nature. To achieve fast and effective results in pencil drawing, teachers recommend regularly working on sketches and drawings. A sketch aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the observed natural environment over a given period. Sketches can vary in length depending on the type of work, the working conditions, and the tasks set by the artist: half an hour, an hour, ten minutes, and so on.

Sketch drawing is a quick drawing from nature. It teaches students to think quickly and find the most reliable and logical means of depiction. It also develops observation.

There are advantages to drawing a still life using a simple pencil. Still life depicts inanimate objects. This genre is characterised by the depiction of everyday items, such as vegetables, fruit and tools. Every artist begins to study the secrets of fine art by working on a still life. The first lesson in studying other aspects and types of art is mastering the shape, form and character of objects and things. However, this does not mean that still life remains only an initial task in art. However, creating a

N. Oydinov, 'Problems of training artist-teachers'. Tashkent: Teacher, Ziyonoshir, 1997. 120 p.

still life as an art form requires its own complex and extensive training.

Just as working on pencil sketches is important for colour painting, working on studies, or colour plates, is also of great importance. 'Before embarking on a long-term project, it is essential to complete a smaller, quickly executed study. This will help you to find a format that suits the composition and overall colour of the still life. Learning to work with colour plates in moderation will help you master the technique of painting. After improving your watercolour skills, you can progress to more complex still lifes. This exercise develops your ability to perceive colours and accurately depict differences in colour tones. Continuing such research will gradually lead to the creation of paintings.

Alongside a close study of the secrets of the fine arts, it is useful to familiarise yourself with the work of famous artists. The artist who worked during the years of independence was a talented master of brushstrokes, as well as a teacher and pedagogue, and is distinguished by the creation of many paintings. He boldly addressed many genres of fine art. He was particularly skilled at creating thematic compositions, landscapes, still lifes and portraits. One integral and

unique aspect of his work is his depiction of still lifes, in which he skillfully captures the generosity of Mother Nature. Looking at the works of Gafir Abdurakhmonov, you will see the beauty in the images. The delicate lines of the landscapes are testament to the artist's exquisite taste. The beauty of the East, with its clean air, land, cypress mountains, lush orchards and vegetation, is masterfully expressed in his works. An artistic analysis of the artist's still life work, 'Grocer', is as follows. When you look at the painting Grocer, created by the Uzbek artist Gafur Abdurakhmanov in the still life genre, you will be plunged into a world of endlessly diverse emotions.

G. Abdurakhmanov "Grocer" still life.

It's like a smile on your face. The work seems to invite you to engage with it. This compositionally complex still life vividly expresses itself through household items, fruit, colourful fabrics and a palette of colours. In the background, there is a traditional copper pot with a melon on top and another melon in the middle of the painting. The artist has arranged the subject in such a way that it is clear he has skilfully applied the principles of still life composition. The scales and weights in the foreground serve to emphasise the subject matter. Additionally, the still life depicts various fruits and household items in a vase. A national rug woven from wool, reminiscent of our past, is also present. The work is perfect in terms of

composition. G. Abdurakhmanov's depiction of the still life 'Grocery' in colour clearly shows the shape, materiality, grain and surface of the objects within it.

The artist worked so skilfully that each object in the picture seems as if you could hold it in your hands. All the objects are depicted in a realistic manner, in the style of a farmer. "Grocery" is considered a masterpiece of still life. Even when viewed casually, the viewer's attention is drawn to the invisible figure behind the copper pot. One cannot help but wonder whether the ruola, whose exterior is depicted in red, was made slightly less visible to make it more interesting, especially for a still life. Alternatively, you may wonder what it would be like if the ruola were fully visible. Clearly, the still life 'Grocer' invites contemplation, reflection and observation.

It is difficult to express in words the positive influence that works of fine art can have on a person's psyche. Of course, each work of art must be seen with the eyes and felt with the heart. In this regard, the following words of Denis Diderot are pertinent: "Any nation that teaches its children to draw as diligently as it teaches literacy, reading, and arithmetic will surpass other nations in science, art, and crafts." This also indicates the important place that fine art occupies in human life.

We considered how important fine art is in human life and how people live in a way that is directly related to it. It is clear from the above that even if not everyone holds a brush in their hands, they still live in a way that is directly related to fine art. Of course, to make our lives more beautiful and meaningful, we must master the secrets of fine art. The more deeply we study the images created by our ancestors, the clearer our understanding of their lives, art and culture becomes.

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